

INCREASE THE INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF THE REGION BASED ON
THE DEVELOPMENT OF INVESTMENT MARKETING

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Abstract: An important strategic task of the region's development is to create a favorable investment environment, its implementation depends on socio-economic dynamics, the efficiency of involvement in the international division of labor, and the possibilities of modernizing the regional economy on an innovative basis. In general, investment attractiveness can be defined as a set of objective and subjective conditions that facilitate or hinder the investment process of the national economy at the macro, meso, and micro levels.

Keywords: product, price, place, promotion, investment attractiveness in Surkhandarya, Statistics Department, numbers of fixed capital investment.

Based on this definition, a number of factors shaping the level of investment attractiveness of the region, including: general economic development (agrarian or industrial area, average wage level in the region), demographic situation (birth rate, death rate, number of scientists with academic degrees, unemployment rate, population number, including those with higher education), investment infrastructure (construction enterprises, energy resources, highways, railways), financial and market infrastructure (non-state enterprises, banks, financial and credit organizations), foreign economic direction (export, import, goods, works, services, capital), we can distinguish man-made, environmental risks (level of pollution, number of harmful productions, economic crimes).

However, as Yu. M. Barsky correctly noted, the main aspect of creating a positive investment environment is the country's image, because the lower its level meets the investor's expectations, the lower the investment environment is evaluated and serves to stabilize the investment environment. In this, of course, every investor will pay attention to the incentives for investments attracted to the country, because the more incentives the state gives, the more investors will be interested. After all, the level of investment attractiveness of the enterprise is determined by the degree of proportionality of the interests of all subjects of the investment process, in particular, the owners of the enterprise, investors, regional authorities and product consumers, and its successful implementation. As part of a socially oriented approach, the concept of regional marketing increases the degree of alignment of interests of institutions participating in the investment process.

According to modern approaches, regional marketing can be defined as a method of establishing, creating and maintaining such relationships with various market entities, which provides the region with resources and advantageous positions in terms of target markets, as well as allows the participants of the relationship to reach this market. This, in turn, makes it possible to distinguish the following features of a regional marketing investment project (of a particular region) that characterize it as an investment product using the tools of the "4R" complex:

- 1) investment attractiveness of the region as the ability of this specific "product" to fully satisfy the investor's needs (similarity with the buyer);
- 2) "Place" should be understood as attracting investments for the implementation of regional programs and projects;
- 3) the amount of investment resources needed by the recipient for project implementation should be specified in the "price" section;
- 4) under "promotion" ("promotion") or "communication" - choosing the optimal scheme of "delivering" information about the investment project to potential investors during the investment process, that is, conveying information to consumers (investors) about the advantages of the product (investment project) and A set of different activities to stimulate the desire to "buy" should be understood.

The established means of regional marketing can be effectively used to create new competitive advantages of a given region, influence the target audience, and thus attract economic agents. In addition, the activation of investment activities in the field of marketing of the region includes:

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- based on the specific features of the region's formation and development, developing programs to form and improve its image and in the future to implement branding as a special means of forming a positive image of the region;

- allows management bodies and some enterprises to significantly increase the value of territories and attract investment resources without increasing current consumption, production volumes, use of natural resources;

- communication activities to increase the attractiveness of natural, material-technical, financial, labor, organizational, social and other resources aimed at increasing foreign investors:

- territorial, as well as the development, operation and image of the territory in the implementation and restoration of such resources depends on their successful operation; media and advertising opportunities should be considered. Such activities can be carried out through the regional marketing center in the form of representatives of event agencies, which are called non-profit partnerships consisting of representatives of regional authorities, owners of leading enterprises. In particular:

- it is also important to provide investors with information through the Internet portal, develop and distribute analytical data, participate in international forums and exhibitions, regularly organize investment-related events in the region;

- organizing and ensuring the effective participation of the region and its subjects in the implementation of international national, regional and interregional programs, as well as in the placement of state and other orders in the region;

- development of the "driver" sectors of industry and full use of the industrial potential of the regions;

- production of import-substituting products by large enterprises and expansion of cooperative relations with regional enterprises,

- introduction of a system of active incentives for enterprises that have established industrial cooperation.

- All-round support for exporters who bring national brands to foreign markets based on the idea of "New Uzbekistan - the country of competitive products";

The investment attractiveness of the Surkhandarya region is related to the geographic location of the region (border, transport) as well as the advantages of natural features and labor potential, which are actively used for the implementation of cross-border infrastructure projects to increase the economic potential of the region and the well-being of the population.

In this regard, if we pay attention to the data of the Statistics Department of Surkhandarya Region, in 2023, 17956.0 billion. Sums of fixed capital investment have been utilized, which has increased by 55.2% compared to the previous year 2022. In 2015, the region received only 191.7 billion. sums of direct foreign investment, by 2023 this indicator will reach 11,114.8 billion. amounted to soum. The highest figure is 3179.3 billion in Boysun district. soums and Sherabad district 3260.9 billion. is achieving positive results by attracting soums. In general, values higher than the regional average (53.0%) in attracting foreign investment and loans are Oltinsoy (58.4%), Angor (60.3%), Bandikhon (59.9%), Boysun (91.8 %), Muzrabot(56.4%), Zharkurgan(64.7%) and Sherabad(90.2%) districts, with US direct foreign investments, their amount was 194.0 dollars per person

In general, when analyzing the investment attractiveness of the region, it is necessary to determine the real investment attractiveness using the tools of the "4R" complex, which allows to

distinguish the descriptive features of the investment project (a separate area) as an investment product. Perspectives in this direction consist in changing regional (territorial) marketing tools for use in forming new competitive advantages of the region to influence the target audience and thus increase the activity of economic entities.

Recently, in scientific works and popular scientific publications, one can find an approach in which the investment project (enterprise) is considered as a specific product. Considering the above, it is possible to consider not only the investment project as a product, but also the entire enterprise. Then the investment attractiveness of the enterprise can be evaluated from the point of view of marketing, and the investment activity of the enterprise as an economic activity that increases the quality of the product.

In the modern activity of the company, the definition of the marketing concept, which includes the market approach to entrepreneurship based on the priority of the consumer as the main agent of market relations, plays an important role. whose inquiries should be directed to marketing activities.

The socially oriented concept of marketing is characterized by the harmony of the interests of producers, consumers and society as a whole. If we consider this concept within the framework of the institutional theory, it should be noted that the implementation of investment activities of various institutions helps to form the investment attractiveness of the enterprise, as well as increases the efficiency of socially oriented marketing processes in the enterprise.

Conclusion: It should be noted that the proposed method for assessing the investment attractiveness of regions is universal, as it includes the main traditional indicators of project efficiency, and therefore is suitable for regions and enterprises of any form of ownership and industry. In addition, taking into account the degree of proportionality of the interests of the subjects of the investment process, it will be possible to analyze the attractiveness of projects in a new way, in connection with which the following advantages will arise.

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